

Tree Discoverable in Curvature and Torsion of Metric Space and its Fourier Compression

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Abstract

[한국어] 어떠한 곡선도 트리 형태로 변환 가능하다. 그리고 여기에 최소 신장 트리 알고리즘을 적용하여 곡선을 나타내기 위한 최소한의 방법을 찾기 위해 푸리에 변환을 기반으로 한 압축 방법도 도입될 수 있다.

[English] Any curvature can be represented in form of tree graph. And with applying minimal spanning tree algorithm unto the tree, Fourier transformation method based compression method for finding minimal expression of tree can be derived.

1 Introduction

As discussed in other article[1], any form of curvature can be in form of Euler's polyhedron. Let's assume this \mathbb{R}^n vector to be in form of matrices products. For each θ_n to be n -th angle for cursion or torsion and l_n to be length of vector in specific axis:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Curvature } C &= (\sin \theta_{1_x} \quad \sin \theta_{2_x} \quad \cdots) \cdot (l_{1_x} \quad l_{2_x} \quad \cdots) \\ &+ (\sin \theta_{1_y} \quad \sin \theta_{2_y} \quad \cdots) \cdot (l_{1_y} \quad l_{2_y} \quad \cdots) \\ &+ (\sin \theta_{1_z} \quad \sin \theta_{2_z} \quad \cdots) \cdot (l_{1_z} \quad l_{2_z} \quad \cdots) \\ &+ \cdots \\ &= (l_{1_x} \sin \theta_{1_x} + l_{1_y} \sin \theta_{1_y} + l_{1_z} \sin \theta_{1_z} + \cdots \quad l_{2_x} \sin \theta_{2_x} + l_{2_y} \sin \theta_{2_y} + l_{2_z} \sin \theta_{2_z} + \cdots \quad \cdots) \end{aligned}$$

2 Minimal Spanning Tree

For Tree T (Vertex V , Edge E), any curvature can be represented in form of upper summation. With aligning each vertex and edge by their own axis, each vertex is defined as marginal error diminished by adding node to another edge and each edge is defined as constituent vector in defining the curve grouped by each axis.

Each content in Table 1 of cell represents loss. With applying minimal spanning tree algorithm unto the graph that table represents, the most efficient case can be selected.

	$l_{1_x} \sin \theta_{1_x}$	$l_{1_y} \sin \theta_{1_y}$	$l_{1_z} \sin \theta_{1_z}$	$l_{2_x} \sin \theta_{2_x}$	$l_{2_y} \sin \theta_{2_y}$	$l_{2_z} \sin \theta_{2_z}$	\cdots
$l_{1_x} \sin \theta_{1_x}$	0	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots
$l_{1_y} \sin \theta_{1_y}$	\cdots	0	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots
$l_{1_z} \sin \theta_{1_z}$	\cdots	\cdots	0	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots
$l_{2_x} \sin \theta_{2_x}$	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	0	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots
$l_{2_y} \sin \theta_{2_y}$	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	0	\cdots	\cdots
$l_{2_z} \sin \theta_{2_z}$	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	\cdots	0	\cdots
\cdots	\cdots						

Table 1: Loss Table from Original to Compression

3 Fourier Transformation

Then how can be the minimal spanning tree's selection can be compared with selecting or not selecting the vertex? The difference can be derived from comparing the number of frequency in Fourier transformation in each minimal spanning tree. With λ being sum total of all edges from Fourier transformation of loss tree with original curvature:

$$n(\text{Vertex } V^*) = \min_{n(\text{Vertex } V)} (\text{Calculated Loss} - \lambda(\text{Tree } T, n(\text{Vertex } V)))$$

And so, method for compressing curvature in minimal spanning tree with Fourier transformation can be postulated.

4 Possible Application

With this concept, A new loss function for deep neural network based on minimal spanning tree in model quantization can be suggested. Application itself is out of context in this paper, but only noted for suggesting further implication.

References

- [1] Jihyeon Yoon. Deriving Euler's Polyhedron Formula from Curvature and Torsion in Metric Space. July 2024.